

ON RESTORATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF COTTON THE POLICY OF THE SOVIET GOVERNMENT (FIRST HALF OF XX CENTURY)

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Abstract: The article analyzes the measures taken by the Soviet government to restore and develop cotton cultivation.

Key words: cotton policy, people's commissariat, irrigation, agronomy, water management

The Soviet state continued the path of the Russian Empire to "turn the country into a cotton raw material base, to transport the grown cotton raw material to Russia in a new ideological shell and mask. It should be noted that the Soviet government implemented measures to develop cotton cultivation, strengthen its material and technical base, restore irrigation networks, develop agricultural cooperation, and increase cotton yield. After all, the Soviet government was interested in the revival of agriculture in Turkestan, first of all, cotton production, and it decided the fate of the main agricultural products grown in the country - cotton, wheat, silk, cotton, leather, wool, dry fruits, etc. Therefore, in order to restore agriculture and increase production, in 1920, 1,234 plows, 128 cultivators, 32,741 sickles, 66 harrows, 22 jodi, 22 hay mowers, 96 seed drills, 128 cultivators, 26 lobogreyka (mowing machines), 12 7 samosbroska (a self-harvesting reaper), 10 threshers, 388 separators (a machine that separates cream from milk), 19,290 sickles were sent[1]. This agricultural equipment was distributed among Syrdarya, Samarkand, Fergana, Ettisuv, Trans-Caspian regions. According to the information of the center, it is planned to send 15 thousand plows, 2 thousand harrows, 400 harvesters, 140 hay harvesters, 140 horse mowers, 75 thousand reapers, 50 thousand sickles, 100 threshing machines to Turkestan.

By the decision of the Board of the People's Commissariat of Agriculture of the Republic of Turkestan on May 23, 1921, agronomy base points were established in order to promote new methods of planting, growing and caring for crops, to fight against the division of agricultural equipment and their inappropriate use [2].

It is envisaged that the agricultural equipment imported from Russia will be given to these bases instead of being distributed to some farms. Agronomy base points were under the uezd land departments. In August 1921, there were 36 agronomic centers in the Republic of Turkestan, including 12 in Fergana region, 11 in Samarkand, 6 in Syrdarya, and 4 beyond the Caspian. In the republic, there were 63 machine rental points and agricultural equipment, workshops for repairing their machines, 13 experimental fields and stations that help farmers in the field of agronomy [3].

Agricultural equipment was sold to farmers through the agricultural warehouses of the Department of Supply under the People's Commissariat of Agriculture in Andijan, Samarkand, Tashkent, Poltaratsk and other cities. Local warehouses were supplied with agricultural machinery and tools by a central warehouse. Warehouses sold 20% of agricultural tools to

landowners for cash, and 80% on easy terms based on a certificate from local land authorities and extended the payment period until harvest.[4].

Based on the requirements of the new economic policy, on April 24, 1922, the Council of People's Commissars of the Republic of Turkestan abolished the state monopoly on the ownership and trade of agricultural machinery, equipment, fertilizers and materials, and allowed them to be sold to the state and cooperatives, as well as to private individuals. Turkgosselsklad, Turkgosselsklad, was established in place of the Department of Supply under the People's Commissariat of Agriculture at the expense of the economy.

In 1922, Turkgosselsklad sold agricultural tools for 67 thousand rubles, and other cooperative organizations for 15 thousand rubles. In 1915, agricultural equipment was sold for 1200 thousand rubles [6]. It can be seen that in 1922 compared to 1915, tools were sold to farmers about 15 times less. Reconstruction of the material and technical base of farming, replacement of traditional labor tools of farmers with new agricultural machinery became important in the development of cotton farming. Special attention began to be paid to this work, especially since 1921. If in 1918-1920, farmers in Central Asia were given only 64 harrows, 173 seeders, 571 cultivators and 375 plows, during 1921-1925 the villagers received 1,063 cultivators, 938 seeders, 8,044 harrows, and 10,116 plows from state supply bodies [7].

On August 28, 1925, the Main Cotton Committee of the USSR, which was interested in the development of the cotton industry, decided to mechanize cotton cultivation in Central Asia and the Caucasus [8].

In the decision, it was demanded to strengthen measures for the development of cotton cultivation and the use of European-type agricultural tools in cotton farms. The main organizations that carry out this work are agricultural cooperatives and bodies of the People's Commissariat of Agriculture. It was envisaged that the People's Commissariats of Agriculture of the cotton-growing republics would develop a program of activities to provide cotton-growing farms with European-style farming tools, and involve the agricultural cooperative and the agricultural bank in the implementation of these activities. Also, People's Commissariats of Agriculture are tasked with solving the issue of how many European-type agricultural tools should be brought to the growing republics, and for this, to study the available financial opportunities, to find the necessary funds for the purchase of agricultural tools.

Taking into account the need of farmers for plowing tools, the shortage and high cost of working animals, the Cotton Committee of Uzbekistan considered it necessary to use tractors in agriculture. The tractors were initially tested on the state farms of this institution. After it was determined that the method of using the tractor was effective in local agricultural conditions, various levels of campaigning were carried out among cotton farmers. They plowed their fields free of charge to demonstrate to the cotton farmers how to plow the land with a tractor and to promote it. After the peasants saw and understood the advantages of plowing with tractors compared to plowing with horses and oxen, the cotton committee formed tractor squads and arranged to plow the land of cotton farms on credit at a low price and with the condition of payment after harvest.

In addition to providing farmers with agricultural tools, tractors were imported from abroad, mainly from the USA. In 1924, Glavkhlopkom sent several "Fordzon" tractors to Uzbekistan in order to test and select those that would meet the requirements of cotton growing. 5 of these tractors were given to the land department of Fergana region. On

September 23-24, 1924, it was decided to distribute one of these tractors to Ko'kan, Andijan, Namangan, Margilon and Osh uezds at the collegiate meeting of the land department [9].

In the spring of 1925, the process of working with a tractor was started in Uzbekistan. According to N.N. Golikov, a specialist in tractorization of the People's Commissariat of Agriculture of Uzbekistan, on November 17, 1927, 156 tractors worked in Uzbekistan in 1923-24, 504 in 1924-25, 1017 in 1925-26, and 1048 in 1926-27[10].

The introduction of European-style agricultural tools to growers and other farms was the focus of attention of agricultural authorities and cooperative organizations. Uzbekgosselsklad organization bought such weapons from Russia and distributed them to farmers. In 1926/27 - 1927/28, 11,660 plows, 10,000 harrows, 5,250 cotton seeders, 6,700 cultivators and okuchniks (harvesting tools) were brought to Uzbekistan[11]. Besides these, agricultural factories "Dehkan" in Samarkand and "Ilich" in Tashkent produced traditional agricultural tools - hoe, scythe and other tools. Agricultural tools are also made in craft workshops and blacksmith workshops belonging to the local industrial association of Uzbekistan. All equipment was distributed to farmers through agricultural cooperatives.

In order to develop cotton cultivation and expand the cotton cultivation areas in Uzbekistan, the state provides cotton farmers with modern European-type working tools. From January 1 to October 1, 1928, the agricultural cooperative distributed 9,882 plows, 2,669 harrows, 7,447 harrows, and 66 seed drills to the farmers of the republic[12].

Artificial irrigation of lands is the basis of agricultural development in the conditions of Turkestan. In the early years of the Soviet power, as a result of the Red Army's struggle against the pro-independence forces, irrigation fountains were destroyed, and the irrigation system - streams, canals, main ditches - was not cleaned and repaired. Irrigation had declined, resulting in a reduction in irrigated cropland. In Fergana region, which is considered the main agricultural region of the country, the total cultivated area was 866 thousand desyatinas in 1915, it decreased to 396 thousand desyatinas in 1919, and 361 thousand desyatinas by 1922, which made up 44.7% of the cultivated area of 1915 in 1919 and 40.7% in 1922.

As a result of the NEP policy, the revival of the industry, including the textile industry, increased the need for cotton raw materials, and demanded the restoration of cotton cultivation in Turkestan and the increase of cotton cultivation. Taking this into account, the Soviet government took measures to urgently restore the cotton industry in Turkestan.

Taking into account that irrigation in Turkestan is in a difficult situation, and the restoration of cotton cultivation depends on the repair of irrigation fountains, the Soviet government allocated 6 million for this work for 1923. allocated soums (in the form of gold coins). This, of course, had a significant impact on the improvement of the irrigation system. This fund provided an opportunity not only for current maintenance, but also for the capital repair of important irrigation canals and the construction of a number of engineering facilities. The works have improved the condition of the canal and main ditches. It halted the reduction of irrigated areas and expanded the cultivated areas, increasing the gross yield of cotton. In 1923, the area under cotton cultivation was 192.8 thousand hectares, and the gross cotton yield was 37.7 thousand tons. Compared to 1922, in 1923, the cotton area was 123.5 thousand hectares, and the gross harvest was 25 thousand tons more[13].

In 1924, the Turkestan Water Management Department received 6.5 million from the union budget. received soums (in the form of gold coins). This fund made it possible to carry

out large-scale irrigation works, important works carried out in 1924; among them, the reconstruction of the head of the Zakh and Khanim canals in the Syrdarya region, strengthening the banks of the Bektemir junction, the repair of the Andijonsoy and Shahrikhansoy canals in the Fergana region, the reconstruction of the Yangiariq system, the repair of the Dargom junction in the Samarkand region, etc.

In 1923 and 1924, along with the increase in budget allocations for the restoration of the irrigation sector, the participation of peasants in the cleaning and maintenance of the irrigation system also increased. Peasant farms in 1923 3.5 mln. days of labor obligation and performed work worth 3.5 million soums, in 1924 he performed 2.5 million days and work worth 3.8 million soums[14].

Carrying out a large-scale restoration program required the training of qualified irrigator personnel. In 1923, an evening hydrotechnical school was opened in Tashkent. In 1924, a full-time hydrotechnical school and a corporal's school were established. In 1923, 8 hydro-remediation engineers graduated from the engineering-reclamation faculty opened in 1922 at the Central Asian State University, and in 1924, 8 more students graduated from this faculty[15].

In the academic year 1923-24, more students were admitted to the engineering-reclamation faculty than in previous years: in April 1924, 136 students studied in the first year of the faculty, 79 in the second year, 39 in the third year, 19 in the fourth year, a total of 258 students [16].

200 students studied at the evening hydrotechnical school of Tashkent, 100 during the day, and 63 students at the corporal school. The duration of study at the technical school was 3.5 years. In December 1924, the first graduation ceremony of students took place at the evening hydrotechnical school[17]. It should be noted that in this way, the system of training engineers and technical hydromeliotrators was founded in Uzbekistan.

The allocation of large amounts of funds by the Soviet government, the provision of qualified personnel to the water management authorities, and the selfless work of irrigators and hardworking farmers made it possible to achieve some progress in the restoration and reconstruction of the irrigation system. The development of irrigation, in turn, led to the expansion of irrigated land, including cotton, and clearly shows that the irrigated land has increased year by year. (Appendix 1)

According to the information of the Turkestan Cotton Committee, the area under cotton cultivation increased from 51 thousand decimeters in 1922 to 152 thousand decimeters in 1923, and in 1924 the cotton area was 300 thousand decimeters. The growth of the cotton area and cotton cultivation was the result of a number of measures taken by the Soviet government to provide the textile industry of the central regions with cotton raw materials, to restore and develop irrigation, to strengthen the material and technical base, to provide material benefits to farmers, to reduce the amount of taxes on cotton crops, and others.

Naturally, thanks to relatively favorable conditions created by the state, cultivated areas in Uzbekistan began to recover rapidly. If in 1923-24 the cultivated area in Uzbekistan was 1009.8 thousand hectares, in 1924-25 it increased to 1144.9 thousand hectares, and in 1925-26 it reached 1240.8 thousand hectares [18]. In 1923/24-1925/26, the cultivated area increased from 60.7% to 74.6%. Taking into account the importance of cotton raw materials for the textile industry of the Soviet state, the Union government paid special attention to the

issue of restoring the cotton sector. The area of cotton cultivation increased from 275,000 deciles in 1924 to 372,100 deciles in 1925[19]. In 1921-1928, certain works were carried out in the field of irrigation in Uzbekistan in order to expand the area of cotton cultivation and increase the raw material of cotton. In turn, the state spent a lot of money on the construction of irrigation and melioration, development of new lands. As a result, canals, main ditches, collectors were restored in all regions of the republic.

The cotton growing companies led by the Turkestan cotton growing committee have also done great work in the field of providing loans to growers. The amount of lending increased year by year, which helped to restore cotton production and strengthen the peasant economy. In December 1922, the All-Russian Central Executive Committee decided to establish the Central Asian Agricultural Bank in order to provide loans to farmers. For this purpose, the Agricultural Bank of Uzbekistan was established, and in the second half of the 20s it was headed by the well-known figure I.Khidiraliyev. His work in this field was promoted throughout the Union as an example[20]. The main task of the agricultural bank was to develop the cotton sector. For this purpose, the bank established agricultural credit companies, through which advances were given to growers and other farmers.

The need for restoration and further development of agriculture, as well as the need to provide extensive state aid to peasant farms destroyed by the Red Army, required the reconstruction of the former cotton cooperative and the establishment of a universal agricultural credit cooperative in its place. At the meeting of representatives of cotton cooperatives held in February 1923, Turkkhlopsyuz was dissolved, and its initial organizations were transferred to the Turkestan Agricultural Cooperatives Association (Turkselsoyuz).

Turkselsoyuz initially served the cotton companies of Turkkhlopsyuz, which was dissolved, and gave advances. Later, he united the companies established by the Central Asian Agricultural Bank, and all agricultural companies came under his control. Thus, Turkselsoyuz became a universal agricultural credit cooperative. At the beginning of 1924, there were 238,488 members of the association, which united and served 869 companies.

Until April 18, 1924, the agricultural bank spent 2,183,076 rubles directly on agricultural loans through Turkselsoyuz and other agricultural cooperatives and state organizations, including loans of 888,028 rubles to agricultural credit companies. Agricultural companies, in turn, gave loans to 52,286 members.

In Uzbekistan in 1925, the role of agricultural cooperation in the organization of cotton planting was great. Farmers began to notice the advantages of being a member of an agricultural cooperative in their practical life. Therefore, the number of cooperative members in Uzbekistan increased from 141,959 to 396,067 from October 1, 1924 to October 1, 1926. By October 1, 1926, out of 654 companies, 540 or 82.4% were engaged in the organization of cotton planting and cultivation. 346,983 or 87.7% of the members of the cooperative engaged in cotton planting. In some cotton-growing regions, cotton companies are up to 97% of all companies, and members of cotton companies are up to 90% of all cooperative members[21]. Agricultural cooperative provided growers and other farms with money, seeds, agricultural tools, grain, fuel and other industrial and food products on the basis of barter. While serving all branches of agriculture, the Universal Agricultural Cooperative paid special attention to cotton growing. The establishment of a specialized cotton cooperative has further improved the work of providing cotton farms with advances. State bodies, cotton-growing organizations

- Glavkhlopkom and its local committees carried out cotton cultivation in individual farmers' farms mainly through cooperation. Agricultural and cotton cooperatives played an important role in supplying Russian textile factories with cotton raw materials.

In 1921-1928, Soviet agricultural and cotton-growing organizations of the republic, on the instructions of the Soviet government, carried out certain works in the field of strengthening the material and technical base of cotton-growing in Uzbekistan, restoring and developing the irrigation system, improving agricultural cooperatives, and achieved some achievements. The implementation of these measures created the necessary conditions for the development of cotton farming and the growth of gross cotton yield. The main goal was to supply textile factories of the USSR with cotton raw materials.

Based on the proposal of the General Cotton Committee, a number of measures were implemented by the Union government in order to quickly restore cotton production in Central Asia. The General Cotton Committee, with the recommendation of the Soviet government, paid special attention to the issue of developing the irrigation sector, reducing the tax on cotton fields, and providing cotton farmers with industrial goods. The focus of attention was on the issue of sufficient supply of grain to cotton farmers in order to squeeze out grain cultivated areas on irrigated lands and plant cotton on these lands. In order to increase the yield of cotton, the committee carried out a wide range of activities, such as providing cotton farmers with mineral and organic fertilizers, expanding scientific research and experimental work, organizing assistance to farmers in the field of agronomy, mechanization of cotton cultivation, and extensive development of agricultural cooperation. They played an important role in the rapid recovery and development of cotton farming in Uzbekistan and other republics, and in meeting the need for cotton raw materials of the textile industry in the central regions.

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